

IBSC

International Bioscience Conference and the
8th International PSU – UNS Bioscience Conference

Towards the SDG Challenges

ONLINE

25–26 November 2021, Novi Sad, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

IBCS2021 is organized jointly by:

PSU FACULTY OF SCIENCE

University Prince of Songkla,
Thailand

University of Novi Sad,
Faculty of Sciences, Serbia

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

631(082)(048.3)
602(082)(048.3)
502/504(082)(048.3)

THE International Bioscience Conference (2021 ; Novi Sad)
[Book of abstracts] / The International Bioscience Conference and the 8th International PSU
- UNS Bioscience Conference IBSC 2021, 25-26 November, 2021 ; [editors Neda Mimica-Dukić,
Slobodanka Pajević, Anamarija Mandić]. - Novi Sad : Prirodno-matematički fakultet, 2021. -
261 str. : ilustr. ; 30 cm

Наћин pristupa (URL): <https://ibsc2021.pmf.uns.ac.rs/ebook-of-abstracts/>. - Registar.

ISBN 978-86-7031-541-9

1. Joint international PSU-UNS Bioscience Conference (6 ; 2021 ; Novi Sad)
а) Пољопривреда -- Зборници -- Апстракти б) Биотехнологија -- Зборници -- Апстракти в)
Животна средина -- Заштита -- Зборници -- Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 53483017

**International Bioscience Conference (IBSC 2021) was supported by
Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the
Republic of Serbia**

Content

Committee	5
Program IBSC 2021 25-26 November	7
ABSTRACTS	
Plenary Lectures	15
Track 1	21
Track 2	88
Track 3	121
Track 4	203
AUTHORS INDEX	252

Committee

Organizing Committee

1. Slobodanka Pajević, President, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
2. Anamarija Mandić, Vice president, University of Novi Sad, Institute of Food Technology, Serbia
3. Srđan Rončević, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
4. Gordana Vlahović, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
5. Ivana Pejović, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
6. Živana Komlenov Mudrinski, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
7. Saša Rakić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
8. Branislava Lalić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia
9. Vesna Mijatović Jovin, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Serbia
10. Biljana Božin, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Serbia
11. Nataša Simin, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
12. Milan Borišev, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
13. Dejan Orčić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
14. Emilija Svirčev, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
15. Danijela Arsenov, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
16. Milan Župunski, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
17. Aleksandra Tubić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
18. Vidak Raičević, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
19. Jovana Grahovac, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Serbia
20. Jaroslava Švarc-Gajić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Serbia
21. Neda Lakić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Serbia
22. Mladen Horvatović, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
23. Oskar Marko, University of Novi Sad, BioSense Institute, Serbia
24. Miloš Ilić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
25. Milana Rošul, University of Novi Sad, Institute of Food Technology, Serbia
26. Nataša Đerić, University of Novi Sad, Institute of Food Technology, Serbia
27. Nemanja Teslić, University of Novi Sad, Institute of Food Technology, Serbia
28. Dejan Čačić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia

Scientific Committee

1. Neda Mimica Dukić, President, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
2. Anchana Prathep, Prince of Songkla University (PSU), Thailand
3. Pimonsri Mittraparp-Arthorn, Prince of Songkla University (PSU), Thailand
4. Sara Bumrungsri, Prince of Songkla University (PSU), Thailand
5. Wipawadee Sianglum, Prince of Songkla University (PSU), Thailand
6. Chongdee Buranachai, Prince of Songkla University (PSU), Thailand
7. Pissared Muangnil, Prince of Songkla University (PSU), Thailand
8. Jaruwan Mayakul, Prince of Songkla University (PSU), Thailand
9. Komwit Surachat, Prince of Songkla University (PSU), Thailand
10. Patamarerk Engsontia, Prince of Songkla University (PSU), Thailand

-
11. Viktor Nedović, Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia
 12. Snežana Đorđević, University Colleague London (UCL), UK
 13. Rudolf Bauer, University of Graz, Faculty of Pharmacy, Austria
 14. Sari Kontunen-Soppela, University of Eastern Finland (UEF), Joensuu, Finland
 15. Carmen Arena, University of Naples Federico II, Italy
 16. Sílvia Rocha, University of Aveiro, Portugal
 17. Declan Troy, The Agriculture and Food Development Authority (TEAGASC), Ireland
 18. Brijesh Tiwary The Agriculture and Food Development Authority (TEAGASC), Ireland
 19. Valerija Dunkić, University of Split, Croatia
 20. Darko Modun, University of Split, Croatia
 21. Olga Tzakou, University of Athens, Greece
 22. Maria Couladis, University of Athens, Greece
 23. Svetlana Kulevanova, University of Skopje, Macedonia
 24. Rossella Russo, University of Calabria, Italy
 25. Guido Jurgenliemk, University of Regensburg, Germany
 26. Saša Orlović, University of Novi Sad, Institute of Lowland Forestry and Environment, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia
 27. Dragana Miladinović, Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Novi Sad, Serbia
 28. Branko Ćupina, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia
 29. Diana Bugarski, University of Belgrade, Institute for Medical Research, Serbia
 30. Nada Kovačević, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Pharmacy, Serbia
 31. Niko Radulović, University of Niš, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
 32. Jasmina Agbaba, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
 33. Jadranka Luković, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
 34. Snežana Radenković, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
 35. Marijana Ačanski, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Serbia
 36. Jelena Pejin, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Serbia
 37. Aleksandar Fišteš, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Serbia
 38. Isidora Samojlik, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Serbia
 39. Biljana Basarin, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
 40. Ivana Beara, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
 41. Nataša Nikolić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
 42. Aleksandra Mišan, University of Novi Sad, Institute of Food Technology, Serbia
 43. Jaroslava Švarc-Gajić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Serbia
 44. Jovan Matović, University of Novi Sad, BioSense Institute, Serbia
 45. Milica Pojić, University of Novi Sad, Institute of Food Technology, Serbia
 46. Suzana Jovanović-Šanta, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
 47. Mihajla Đan, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Science, Serbia
 48. Silvana Andrić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia
 49. Jelica Simeunović, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia

T3-P-32 Quantitative structure – ADME properties relationship of boeravinones A-J

Nataša Milošević¹⁰¹, Maja Milanović¹⁰¹, Nebojša Pavlović¹⁰¹, Larisa Đurić¹⁰¹, Nunzio Antonio Cacciola¹⁰²,
Francesca Borrelli¹⁰³, Nataša Milić¹⁰¹

KEYWORDS: medicinal herb; QSPR; drug design; lipophilicity; polarity

INTRODUCTION:

Boeravinones A-J, rotenoids extracted from Indian ayurvedic herb, *Boerhaavia diffusa* are identified as potent antioxidants, spasmolytics as well as inhibitors of the BCRP multidrug transporter and their structure has been confirmed by ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy. However, most of the drug candidates do not meet the expected strict criteria for new drugs and only 4.3% of them proceed from the preclinical stage to the Phase III trial with a positive outcome. The main causes for high attrition rates are toxicity, inadequate pharmacokinetics and low bioavailability. Therefore, it is crucial to optimize the ADME (absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion) profile of the new drug candidates and to understand how structural changes can affect their pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic relationship.

OBJECTIVES:

To conduct *in silico* analysis of physico-chemical properties and ADME behaviour for ten boeravinones.

METHOD / DESIGN:

In silico analysis of molecular properties and pharmacokinetic characteristics of ten boeravinones (A-J) was conducted based on their structure. Molecular properties of the analysed boeravinones as fraction of sp³ hybridized carbon atoms (Fsp³) and polar surface area (PSA) were determined by SwissADME software. Software pkCSM was applied for the calculation of lipophilicity (logP), the percent of intestinal absorption (%IA), volume of distribution in stationary state (Vdss), fraction of unbound compound (FU) for plasma proteins, permeation through blood brain barrier (log BB) and skin permeability (logKp).

RESULTS:

The percent of intestinal absorption (%IA) of boeravinones A-J can be presented as a linear function ($r^2=0.803$, $p<0.001$) of lipophilicity expressed as logP. Distribution parameters such as volume of distribution in stationary state (Vdss) and fraction of drug unbound to plasma proteins (FU) were statistically significant associated to molecular flatness expressed as fraction of sp³ hybridized carbon atoms (Fsp³). Both Vdss and FU can be described as parabolic function of Fsp³ ($r^2=0.920$, $p<0.001$ and $r^2=0.661$, $p=0.009$) for boeravinones A-J. The permeability through different membranes was governed by the polarity of boeravinones A-J quantified as PSA. Additionally, the permeability through the brain-blood barrier (logBB) and the skin (logKp) were correlated with PSA with high statistical quality ($r^2=0.816$, $p=0.001$ and $r^2=0.729$, $p=0.004$) and the parabolic functions were also obtained.

CONCLUSIONS:

Pharmacokinetic behaviour of boeravinones A-J based on *in silico* analysis is strongly affected by their physico-chemical characteristics. Lipophilicity governs the intestinal absorption of the analysed boeravinones, while the distribution process

¹⁰¹ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia. Corresponding author: natasa.milosevic@mf.uns.ac.rs

¹⁰² University of Naples Federico II, Department of Veterinary Medicine and Animal Productions, Naples, Italy

¹⁰³ University of Naples Federico II, School of Medicine and Surgery, Department of Pharmacy, Naples, Italy

is depended mainly on their flatness. Polarity of the observed boeravinones controls their permeability through different membranes, and limits their permeation through both the blood-brain barrier and the skin. The obtained results are applicable only for investigated structurally homogenous series of boeravinones A-J and should not be taken for general predictions.

T3-P-33 *In silico* prediction of boerhaavia diffusa rotenoids potential to inhibit breast cancer resistance protein (BCPR)

Nataša Milošević, Maja Milanović, Nebojša Pavlović, Nataša Milić¹⁰⁴

KEYWORDS: medicinal herb; QSAR; drug design; BCPR; *in silico*

INTRODUCTION:

Breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP) is a member of the ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporter family. BCRP transporter extracts the chemotherapeutics from the tumour cells and thus reduces the therapeutic efficiency of chemotherapeutics. It was found on the membranes of various carcinoma cells including fibrosarcoma, glioblastoma, myeloma, colon breast and gastric carcinoma. Nonprenylated rotenoids from *Boerhaavia diffusa* (boeravinones and coccineones) were experimentally identified as possible BCRP inhibitors. Their structure has been confirmed by ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy.

OBJECTIVES:

To investigated the interaction profile of thirteen compounds (boeravinones A-J, coccineones B and E, and 6-O-demethylboeravinone H) as BCRP transporter inhibitors.

METHOD / DESIGN:

Vienna LiverTox Workspace online tool was applied to investigate the interaction of thirteen rotenoids from *B.diffusa* with BCRP and to predict whether these molecules inhibit BCRP or not. A score close to 1 indicates a high probability of being an inhibitor while a score close to 0 indicates a high probability of not being an inhibitor. Molecular flatness for the analyzed rotenoids expressed as fraction of sp³ hybridized carbon atoms (Fsp³), polar surface area (PSA) and lipophilicity (XlogP₃, WlogP, MlogP) were determined by SwissADME software.

RESULTS:

Only boeravinone B, E and F were predicted as BCRP inhibitors by Vienna LiverTox Workspace online tool. However, previously published results indicated that boeravinones A, B, C, E, G, H, I, J, coccineones B and E as well 6-O-demethylboeravinone H are BCPR inhibitors. Experimentally obtained results for BCPR inhibition published previously and *in silico* derived predictions were consistent only for boeravinones B and E. Boeravinone F was predicted to be BCPR inhibitor via Vienna LiverTox Workspace which is inconsistent with experimentally obtained results. Moreover, nine more rotenoids were experimentally proven to accumulate mitoxantrone that was not predicted by the Vienna LiverTox Workspace. Vienna LiverTox Scores for analysed thirteen rotenoids were linearly related with the flatness (Fsp³) of the molecules with statistical significance ($r^2=0.334$, $p=0.023$). Also, polarity was correlated with Vienna LiverTox Scores for all observed rotenoids and parabolic function was obtained with high statistical quality ($r^2=0.611$, $p=0.003$). However, no association was obtained between Vienna LiverTox Scores and lipophilicity (XlogP₃, WlogP or MlogP) of the investigated rotenoids.

¹⁰⁴ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia. Corresponding author: natasa.milosevic@mf.uns.ac.rs